

Removal and kinetics of succinic acid from aqueous waste over NaOH treated power plant fly-ash

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Abstract : Waste water containing succinic acid pose grave problems to the environment. As organic molecules are recalcitrant to bio degradation and difficult to treat by conventional methods, the effective removal from pollution generating sites is essential to prevent environmental hazards. In this study, fly ash from coal burning power plant was activated chemically and used as a low cost adsorbent for the removal of succinic acid from the aqueous waste. The activated fly ash was characterized for mineralogical, physiochemical and morphological properties by XRD, FT-IR and SEM analysis. Results showed that activated fly ash due to increased amorphous property possesses more activity over surface to act as a suitable adsorbent for the removal of acidic waste from industrial effluents. This application of fly ash to synthesize a low cost adsorbent, also finds a noble way to utilize this abundant waste material.

Keywords : Chemical activation, fly ash, succinic acid, adsorption.

Introduction

The current worldwide use of succinic acid is around 20000 to 30000 tonnes per year and this is on increase by around 10% per year. The succinic acid has been used in number of industries including polymers¹ (clothing fiber), petrochemicals, food, surfactants and detergents, flavor and fragrances, as a starting material for large number of chemicals, applied in pharmaceutical industries². Owing to its wide applications in various industries, succinic acid is present as waste in toxic effluents emerging out of such industries and influences the properties of soil and aquatic environment receiving industrial waste³.

Fly-ash, a finely divided powdered byproduct from coal fired plant or biomass combustion facilities require ultimate disposal. The major constituents of fly-ash are silica, alumina, iron oxide, lime, magnesia and alkali in varying amounts with some unburnt activated carbon. Besides these, some minor elements such as Hg, As, Ge, Ga and traces of heavy metals (Cr, Co, Cu, Pb, Mn, Ni, Zn)⁴ and rare earths may also be present in fly ash. The glassy (amorphous) siliceous spherical particulates are the

active portion of fly ash. Typically, fly ash is 30–50% glass and higher glass content in the form of quartz is also present in it⁴. Other metal oxides such as Mn₂O₃, TiO₂ etc.⁵ and minerals like mullite, hematite, ferrite and rutile in fly ash⁶ are desirable from the point of view of reactivity.

Fly-ash has been employed as a low cost adsorbent for flue gas and water cleaning^{7–12} and many efforts have been made focused on heavy metals^{13,14} and dye adsorption^{15,16} on fly-ash particles. However no investigation has been reported on organic acids. In this paper, we report the use of fly-ash as an adsorbent by activating it, for the complete removal of succinic acid from aqueous waste. Batch adsorption studies were carried out systematically and attempts have also been made to understand the adsorption equilibrium and kinetics.

Results and discussion

Characterization of adsorbent :

XRD analysis :

The presence of quartz, mullite and calcite is wit-

nessed in both FA and AFA (Fig. 1). Crystallite size was decreased from 33 nm to 11 nm on NaOH treatment. It is

diffraction peaks which are different from those present in untreated one. The diffractograms show that the origi-

Fig. 1(a). XRD of pure fly-ash.

Fig. 1(b). XRD of alkali activated fly-ash.

evident from XRD study that chemical activation has removed most of the crystalline component present in the pure fly-ash thus lowering the crystallinity of the sample and increasing amorphous nature showing the presence of nanocrystalline phase in the sample. Previous studies have shown that fly ash after alkali treatment gives sharp

crystalline phases of fly ash are quartz and mullite which is mostly absent in zeolite material after NaOH treatment of fly ash¹⁷.

SEM analysis :

Figs. 2(a) and (b) show the scanning electron microscopic images of pure and activated FA respectively. In

Fig. 2(a). SEM photograph of pure fly-ash.

Fig. 2(b). SEM photograph of alkali activated fly-ash.

addition to the general physical characteristics and the elemental composition of random population of fly-ash, the SEM data clearly indicate intermixing of silica and alumina phases and predominance of Ca and other

nonsilicate minerals. These results support the data obtained from XRD.

Fig. 2(a) reveals that in the FA, the size of particles range from 840 nm to 10 μm and the majority of particles ranged in 1 μm to 100 μm , consisted of solid sphere, hollow cenosphere, irregularly shaped unburnt carbon particles and mineral aggregates and agglomerated particles which after alkali treatment (Fig. 2b) resulted into scattered agglomerated particles conferring the increase in amorphous property. These results supported data obtained from previous studies¹⁸ and were consistent with XRD data.

FT-IR analysis :

In alkali activation process higher concentration of -OH group favors the breaking of Si-O-Si, Al-O-Al and Si-O-Al bonds and formation of Si-OH and Al-OH groups which is confirmed by a broad band between 3400–3000 cm^{-1} attributed to the presence of surfacial hydroxyl groups (-OH) and adsorbed molecules on the surface. The broadening of a band is due to the strong hydrogen bonding. Signals at 996 cm^{-1} , 1081 cm^{-1} , 1185 cm^{-1} is attributed respectively to the vitreous phases of unreacted fly-ash, quartz and mullite while a new component appearing at around 1025–1006 cm^{-1} is attributed to the sodium aluminosilicate¹⁹ which is also confirmed by some previous studies²⁰.

Fig. 3(a). FT-IR spectra of pure fly-ash.

Fig. 3(b). FT-IR spectra of alkali activated fly-ash.

Adsorption isotherms :

To optimize the design of an adsorption system for the adsorption of adsorbate, the most appropriate correlation for the equilibrium curve are Langmuir and Freundlich. The Langmuir isotherm is valid for monolayer adsorption onto a surface containing a finite number of identical sites

$$Q_c = \frac{Q_0 b C_e}{(1 + b C_0)} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{or } m/x = \frac{1}{Q_0} + \frac{1}{Q_0 b C_e} \tag{2}$$

where C_e is the equilibrium concentration in mg/L and Q_0 is the solid phase concentration corresponding to complete coverage of adsorption sites, b is the Langmuir constant which indicates the nature of adsorption and indicates the shape of the isotherm accordingly. The essential characteristics of a Langmuir isotherm can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless separation factor (r)^{21,22} which describes the type of isotherm and is defined by eq. (3),

$$r = \frac{1}{(1 + b C_0)} \tag{3}$$

Linearised Freundlich adsorption isotherm equation is given by eq. (4),

$$\log q_e = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e \tag{4}$$

where q_e is the amount of acid adsorbed per unit weight

of adsorbent (mg/g), K_f and $1/n$ are the Freundlich constants related to adsorption capacity and intensity respectively. On applying the isotherm eqs. (2) and (4) on experimental results constants were calculated from graphical plots shown in Fig. 4. Values of constants are given in Table 1.

Fig. 4. (a) Langmuir isotherm. (b) Freundlich isotherms.

10 ⁻³ [Acid] (mol dm ⁻³)	Langmuir constants				Freundlich constants	
	<i>b</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>Q</i> ₀	<i>R</i> ²	<i>K</i> _f	1/ <i>n</i>
5	1.3054	0.16	14.084	1.0	41.619	0.4546
10	0.6847	0.16	27.247	1.0	110.17	0.4626
50	0.1314	0.17	121.95	1.0	1185.7	0.4958

The adsorption data were also fitted at five different kinetic models viz. zero order, first order, Elovich equation, parabolic diffusion equations and two rate constants. All the model equations were plotted and tested using least square regression analysis. The values of slope, correlation coefficient (R^2) and standard errors of estimate (SEE) are given in Table 2. On the basis of high R^2 and

Table 2. Coefficient of determination (R^2), standard error of estimate (SEE), and slope for graphical equation of different kinetic models applied on succinic acid adsorption on [AFA] at 30 °C

[Acid] = 5×10^{-3} mol dm $^{-3}$, [AFA] = 2 g dm $^{-3}$			
Kinetic models	R^2	SEE	Slope
Zero order $C_0 - C_t = a - bt$	0.708	0.3887	-0.109
First order $\ln(C_0 - C_t) = a - bt$	0.9275	0.2223	-0.1561
Elovich equation $C_t = a - b \ln t$	0.7692	0.4402	-0.2005
Parabolic diffusion $C_t = a - b t^{1/2}$	0.3832	0.5755	-0.3236
Two rate constant $\ln C_t = \ln k + 1/m \ln t$	0.6903	0.0234	-0.0149

low SEE, the most favourable model to describe the adsorption kinetics is first order kinetic model (Fig. 5). While parabolic diffusion and two rate constant models are completely rejected.

Fig. 5. First order kinetic model plot for succinic acid.

Kinetics of adsorption :

Kinetics of succinic acid removal over AFA is studied by varying concentration of succinic acid, AFA and temperature. Time vs percentage adsorption graph shows initial rapid adsorption in both cases i.e. acid variation and AFA variation. Initial slope is used for determining initial rate (R_{obs}). From the log-log plots of R_{obs} vs succinic acid and R_{obs} vs AFA, an order of 1.0 and 0.5 \pm

0.03 is achieved for dependence of rate on succinic acid and AFA respectively.

Incorporating functional dependence of rate on [acid] and [AFA], the final rate law is given in eq. (5),

$$R_{obs} = k[(CH_2)_2(COOH)_2] [AFA]^{0.5} \quad (5)$$

The value of k is calculated to be 0.46 ± 0.23 g $^{-0.5}$ dm $^{1.5}$ s $^{-1}$ from the plot of R_{obs} with $[AFA]^{0.5}$. Temperature was varied from 25–35 °C. The values of K determined at different temperature were used to plot Arrhenius equation. From the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 6) the value of activation energy was calculated to be 39.15 \pm 1.95 kJ mol $^{-1}$.

Fig. 6. Arrhenius equation plot for succinic acid adsorption

Experimental

Class F fly-ash was collected from KSTPS (Kota Super Thermal Power Plant), Rajasthan for the present study. The catalyst has been synthesized by adding 0.05 N NaOH to the pure fly-ash sample in a fixed ratio. Chemical activation was carried out by continuous stirring of a mixture (NaOH and FA) for 3 h at 90 °C. The fly ash was filtered of, washed repeatedly with distilled water to a neutral pH and dried finally in an oven at 100 °C for 24 h.

Both the initial i.e. pure fly-ash (FA) and the residue obtained after alkaline treatment i.e. activated fly ash (AFA) were characterized mineralogically and microstructurally. Using Philips Expert XRD, samples for determining crystallite size were scanned at 2θ range of 0–80 °C at a scanning rate of 0.04 s $^{-1}$ 23 . FT-IR spectra of both the samples were recorded in the range 400–4000 cm $^{-1}$ with a resolution of 4 cm $^{-1}$. Specific surface area, pore volume and pore size in the sample were determined from N $_2$ adsorption-desorption isotherms using NOVA 1000E surface area analyzer at 77 K. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was performed in the temperature range 50 °C to 1000 °C using model Mettler To-

ledo. To determine the morphology, external surface structures and external elemental distribution of individual FA particle, scanning electron microscope (Philips XL 30 ESEM TMP) has been used.

In the batch method, 50 mL of aqueous succinic acid solution was taken into an Erlenmeyer flask and allowed to attain the desired temperature by circulating thermostated water around the reaction vessel. To initiate the reaction, a fixed amount of AFA as adsorbent (2 g dm^{-3}) was added and stirred continuously at about 1400 ± 1 rpm. The kinetics was followed by withdrawing 0.05 dm^3 aliquot sample at different intervals. The adsorbent was separated from aliquot by simple filtration, concentration of succinic acid was then estimated titrating with standard NaOH solution using phenolphthalein as an indicator. Temperature was varied for estimating activation energy. Experimental runs were observed with initial rapid adsorption trends for a period of 0.5 min to 2.5 min.

Conclusion :

The adsorption catalyst AFA synthesized during this work is found to have sufficient activity to remove succinic acid. Kinetic rate law has given first order with respect to initial concentration and a fractional order of 0.5 ± 0.03 for [AFA] at $30 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A high value of activation energy indicates chemisorption to be important in case of using AFA than physisorption. The study generates fly-ash catalyst for waste water treatment in lubricants, plasticizer, pharmaceutical industries etc. where succinic acid remains as waste in the effluent.

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